

COREnect final roadmap is out!

How should Europe address future connectivity technologies and achieve European leadership in microelectronics and connectivity with a value-chain approach?

Find the dedicated webpage for such a significant milestone!

[COREnect Roadmap](#)

An Action Plan for European Leadership in Digital Infrastructures 16.06.2022

The COREnect Policy Workshop brings together stakeholders from the microelectronics and connectivity domains, from public authorities as well as private organisations, to discuss the priorities and recommendations from the COREnect roadmap.

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Telecommunications and microelectronics: How should Europe (re)-act? 07.06.2022

This workshop aims to present the key findings of these EGs (i.e., a roadmap on how Europe should (re)act in this area) to a broad ICT audience. Moreover, after 2 years of intensive activities, COREnect's recommendations will be presented. A panel of leading experts in the area will discuss the feasibility of these recommendations.

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COREnect is planning a Press Release!

Stay tuned to the COREnect website and social media channels for more details in the upcoming day!

COREnect
www.corenect.eu
info@corenect.eu

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